

Australian Child and Youth Wellbeing Atlas – ACYWA (formerly National Child Health and Development Atlas - ANCHDA)

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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CONTENTS

1	PROJECT INFORMATION	2
1.1	Background	3
1.2	Achievement of project aims	3
2	DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS	5
2.1	Achievements against project work packages:	5
2.2	Project outputs	9
2.3	Outreach and training activities	14
3	SUSTAINABILITY PLAN	15
4	FAIR	17
4.1	Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines	17
5	PROJECT IMPACT	19
5.1	Communications and Engagement	19
5.2	Research Outcomes Planning	22
6	LESSONS LEARNED	23
6.1	What Went Well?	23
6.2	What Could be Improved?	24

1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP728
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - Dec 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	University of Western Australia
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	<p>Australian Human Rights Commission – National Children’s Commissioner</p> <p>Australian Institute of Health and Welfare</p> <p>Australian Research Alliance for Children and Youth</p> <p>Child Unlimited</p> <p>Children’s Health Queensland</p> <p>Commissioner for Children and Young People Western Australia</p> <p>Commissioner for Children and Young People Tasmania</p> <p>Curtin University</p> <p>Deakin University</p> <p>Edith Cowan University</p> <p>Government of WA, Department of Health</p> <p>Kids to Adults National Alliance</p> <p>Murdoch Children’s Research Institute</p> <p>Neuropower</p> <p>Queensland Family and Child Commission</p> <p>Queensland Government Department of Communities, Housing and Digital Economy</p> <p>Queensland University of Technology</p> <p>Telethon Kids Institute</p> <p>The Ian Potter Foundation</p> <p>The Children’s Commissioner Northern Territory</p> <p>Thriving Queensland Kids Partnership</p> <p>Torrens University</p> <p>University of New South Wales</p> <p>University of Sydney</p> <p>Western Australia Department of Premier and Cabinet</p>
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	A/Prof Rebecca Glauert

1.1 Background

With nearly 8 million children and young people in Australia, their wellbeing and future productivity form the cornerstone upon which Australia's future is built. Unfortunately, important data on this demographic is scattered across various locations within our country and its jurisdictions, presenting a difficult challenge to obtaining a comprehensive understanding without considerable investment in both effort and (financial) resources.

The lack of a centralised source for information makes it impossible to paint a holistic picture of children and young people, hindering the ability to make effective, efficient, and evidence-based decisions. To address this issue, researchers, policy makers, service providers, and community members must have access to robust data on children and young people.

Recognising the significance of the communities in which children live, it becomes evident that their geographical context plays a crucial role in shaping their wellbeing. However, the absence of a singular repository for accessing comprehensive data on children and young people complicates efforts across multiple sectors. Valuable time and resources are expended by Government entities, research institutions, non-governmental organisations, and communities in attempting to access data that remains essentially "locked up."

Efficiency and collaboration are imperative in consolidating these dispersed data sources, ensuring a unified and accessible platform for stakeholders. By streamlining access to information, we can empower communities as well as decision-makers and support the wellbeing of Australia's children and young people, laying the groundwork for a more informed and responsive future.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The project aimed to address the critical importance of the health, wellbeing, and future productivity of children and young people in Australia by accelerating access to and the use of data on their health and wellbeing. The project brought together various groups from the academic, government, and not-for-profit sectors across the country that had developed innovative tools for data collation, visualisation, and analysis to advance research, service planning, and policy development related to child health and wellbeing.

The key aims of the project were successfully achieved:

Creation of a National Data Asset: The project successfully consolidated Commonwealth, State, and non-government organisation data relevant to the health and wellbeing of Australian children and young people by creating the first Australian Child and Youth Wellbeing Atlas. This comprehensive data asset serves as a new foundation for informed decision-making in research, planning, and initiatives

focused on child and young people's health and wellbeing. The Atlas is a free mapping resource allowing equitable access to and utilisation of data.

Development of a Proof-of-Concept Dashboard: A proof of concept dashboard, better referred to as a visualisation platform, was built with geospatial and temporal visualisation of a wide range of indicators at both community and state/territory levels. The new platform provides a user-friendly interface for stakeholders to access and interpret data, fostering a better understanding of child and young people's health and wellbeing metrics. User design workshops informed the platform's design, and a separate data download utility was developed for in-depth analysis and comparison of the data across states and territories.

Implementation of Harmonised Data Management Processes: The project implemented harmonised data management, sharing, privacy, and governance processes across various data providers. Despite challenges in navigating the fragmented and diverse child health and wellbeing data landscape, the Atlas project ensured consistency and security in handling data for all indicators in the proof-of-concept platform, promoting collaboration among the entities involved. However, there is ongoing work to navigate the data landscape, particularly in including more state-based health and wellbeing data from children and young people. More work also needs to be done to enable inclusion of data from First Nations children and young people, considering Indigenous data governance and sovereignty protocols.

Identification of Gaps, Priorities, and New Directions: The project successfully identified numerous gaps, priorities, and new directions in multiple fields related to information and data relating to children and young people's health and wellbeing. This insight provides valuable information for researchers, state and federal organisations, and the community to focus on critical areas that require attention and intervention.

Coordination for Major Disruptions: The project established the first Australian Child and Youth Wellbeing Atlas, serving as a proof-of-concept for a coordinated resource to monitor and respond to major disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and climate change. The platform's monitoring capability allows for swift responses and adaptive strategies to address emerging challenges affecting children and young people's health and wellbeing.

The unique Australian Child and Youth Wellbeing Atlas is a dynamic data asset empowering stakeholders to make evidence-based decisions for the wellbeing of Australia's children and young people.

By reducing the natural fragmentation of data resulting from state-based health and other services, the project improves the likelihood of Australian children and young people receiving necessary healthcare, intervention, and research attention.

Moreover, the Atlas promotes transparency and accountability by providing a comprehensive and accessible repository of information. Stakeholders, including policymakers, analysts, researchers, and

community members, can navigate and analyse data relevant to child health and wellbeing, leading to a more transparent understanding of the issues affecting this demographic. This transparency, in turn, holds decision-makers accountable for their actions and policy implementations, as the data becomes a shared resource for scrutiny and evaluation.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
Create ANCHDA branding	ANCHDA branding has been completed. Note: As of June 2023, ANCHDA has been re-branded as ACYWA.	30/06/2021
Create 2 page flyer	2 page flyer has been completed	30/06/2021
Create ANCHDA website	ANCHDA website has been completed	31/12/2021
Establish ANCHDA network	ANCHDA network has been established	31/03/2022
Audit State-based child mapping initiatives	This audit has been completed and the document circulated to the network.	31/03/2021
Audit of child health and wellbeing indicators	This audit has been completed and the document circulated to the network.	31/04/2021

Audit data collections	This audit has been completed and the document circulated to the network	30/06/2022
Audit of approvals and governance issues	Requirements for all proposed indicators were evaluated. Cases of application process challenges, non-approvals, or deemed unattainable within the project timeline were documented.	30/11/2023
Audit report	This report has been completed and presents a summary of the above listed individual audit documents.	30/06/2022
Key data collections and indicators for inclusion	Completed	31/04/2022
Ethics approvals	Completed - ethics approval received from Queensland University of Technology (QUT) for the ANCHDA prototype.	02/12/2022
Data approvals	Completed for all included data sets	09/11/2023
Platform	Officially launched: https://australianchildatlasmap.sph.uwa.edu.au	28/11/2023
Identify and invite key stakeholders	Completed	30/09/2022
Host workshop	Completed. Ten workshops with approx. 40 participants were held. A separate session with young people was also facilitated.	30/11/2022
Workshop report	Completed	31/03/2023

Receive phased delivery of data	Completed	30/05/2023
Data cleaning	Completed	10/06/2023
Create health indicators	Completed	10/06/2023
Data uploading into platform	Completed – however data will continue to be added for new data sets	30/10/2023
Determine and acquire software to develop Atlas	Completed. The Atlas utilises MapBox code.	30/05/2023
Design and plan layout of Atlas	Completed	30/05/2023
Obtain/create required shapefiles for Atlas	Completed	30/05/2023
Create maps for pilot Atlas	Completed	30/10/2023
Conduct tests of pilot Atlas with project team	Completed	30/09/2023
Design and layout of website	Completed: https://australianchildatlas.com	01/10/2023
Create pages for web platform	Completed	01/11/2023

Create Atlas documentation	Completed	01/11/2023
Pilot testing	Completed	16/10/2023
Evaluation	Completed	30/10/2023
Consultation	Completed	30/10/2023
Evaluation report	Completed	30/10/2023
Receive additional datasets	Completed	31/05/2023
Data cleaning	Completed	31/05/2023
Revise Atlas based on feedback	Completed	17/11/2023
Launch Atlas	Completed	28/11/2023
Build a supplementary digital capability embedded within the asset that records user information, activity and engagement. I.e.	Completed – GA script and analytics reports	30/10/2023

Geotagging user locations, frequency of visits, hours spent on the platform, organisations represented		
Design and implement user survey	Not completed – will not impact project outcomes	

2.2 Project outputs

1. Audit of current State-based initiatives and data collections, e.g. data inclusions, format of Atlases, platforms used, status of ethics approvals and governance arrangements

A full audit was carried out and the following audit documents produced and circulated to the project governance groups:

I. Review of child wellbeing indicators and measures:

This audit document summarised the examination of both Australian national and State-based child health and wellbeing frameworks. It systematically aligned their associated indicators with the six wellbeing domains outlined in the Nest framework. The comprehensive mapping exercise extended to ARACY’s Nest framework, the COAG Health Council’s Healthy, Safe, and Thriving national strategy framework, AIHW’s Child Headline Indicators, and National Youth Information framework. Additionally, two State-based frameworks, namely the WA Child Development Atlas and the WA Wellbeing Monitoring Framework, underwent a thorough mapping process. While other State-based frameworks were briefly summarised, their inclusion added depth to the overall assessment.

Furthermore, this audit document offered a concise list detailing relevant national data collections, their data availability, and current status, providing a comprehensive overview of the existing landscape.

II. Review of child mapping initiatives and visualisation platforms:

This audit document conducted a comprehensive review of Australian State-based child mapping initiatives. Acknowledging the limited number of these initiatives, the examination extended to other mapping initiatives that incorporate visualisation techniques. The reviewed applications, chosen from diverse categories such as child health and development, population health, and social and environmental health, contributed to a holistic assessment.

The primary objective of this audit was to pinpoint effective mapping and visualisation techniques that could enhance the presentation of child health and development data within the ACYWA (formerly

ANCHDA) Atlas. By broadening the scope to include various other mapping initiatives, the document aimed to identify innovative approaches that could inform and elevate the quality and impact of visualising child-related data, ensuring a more comprehensive and insightful representation.

III. Review of status of ethics approvals and governance arrangements:

This review process was organised around the six wellbeing domains and their associated indicators (or themes), recognising the complexity involved. However, due to the extensive range of approvals and agreements required across various indicators and jurisdictions, achieving a fully comprehensive review posed challenges.

In developing the Atlas prototype, we conducted a thorough assessment of requirements for all proposed indicators. In instances where the application process faced hurdles, was unsuccessful, or was deemed unachievable within the current project timeline, we documented these cases. These documented challenges serve as markers for future work, allowing for a strategic approach to address them in future phases of the project.

2. Agreement regarding key data collections/indicators and platform to be used; Decision about where the data will be hosted; Ethics approvals, and access arrangements

Decisions on data collections, indicators, and platform selection were based on information gathered in the audit documents. The collaborative efforts and decision-making processes with the Oversight Group, Partnership Group, and Working Groups were instrumental in arriving at these decisions. Upon thorough consideration, it was determined that both raw and cleaned data for the Atlas would be housed at the University of Western Australia in the UWA Research Repository and the UWA OneDrive platform.

Ethics approval and data sharing agreement processes were also shaped by insights from the audit documents, evolving through continuous discussions within the governance groups and working groups throughout the data collection process.

Importantly, a decision was made to subcontract particular responsibilities outlined in the Head Agreement to Queensland University of Technology (QUT). These responsibilities included tasks such as preparing the User Experience and Visualisation Design, the Atlas Software Development, and the Atlas Deployment and Performance Evaluation. This decision was motivated by QUT's proven expertise in this domain, notably demonstrated through their design work on the Australian Cancer Atlas and other visualisation platforms noted in the audit documents. This strategic delegation of responsibilities significantly improved the efficiency and expertise dedicated to various parts of the Atlas project.

3. User design workshop to inform the construction and content of the Atlas

In order to inform the design of the visual and interactive elements of the Atlas, twelve user design workshops were conducted with 34 participants. The user design workshops were recorded and transcribed. A thematic analysis was conducted, and 1,480 excerpts were coded with one of 16 codes.

The results demonstrated that the system that ACYWA represents is complex with multiple data types, geographic units of analysis, and time periods all needed in order to make a range of types of decisions for several end users. The findings showed that the children's health and wellbeing system is disjointed in terms of data, geography, disaggregation and priority areas.

There is a lack of consistency in practices related to data for the different user groups and a lack of approaches to communicating and making decisions with the data connected to these mixed methods approaches. The representations of data are for analysing or reporting the distinct parts (e.g. location or population or health) rather than to connect these parts.

The background questionnaire showed that most participants identified the main role of ACYWA in relation to providing access to data and tools for exploration to have an impact on outcomes for children's health and development.

The practices of the participants regarding the use of maps were not consistent, significant challenges with access to the data they required, they were unable to link this to other data sets and encountered barriers to sharing this data.

The results of the user design workshops identified the following design elements for inclusion:

- Utilise multiple representations that are aligned with the multidisciplinary approaches that are valued within this system;
- Include interactive features to encourage exploration and build capacity of all users to understand complex systems;
- Provide insight into connections between the emergent nature of complex systems within high level infrastructure;
- Represent the dynamic nature of the system particularly including the time delay in feedback loops between action and impact.

4. Data delivery, pooling, cleansing, harmonising of data collections and scale into single platform (Project Officer and Data Scientist/GIS Specialist)

This work package was delivered by a collaborative Data Science team comprising more than six members and including data scientists from both UWA and QUT. Instead of relying on a single full-time or nearly full-time data analyst or scientist, the team-oriented approach proved highly effective. The Data Science team worked seamlessly across various stages of the Atlas data lifecycle, including data

collection, pooling, cleaning, coding, harmonising, quality assurance, and data upload. This collaborative effort ensured comprehensive coverage and expertise at each step of the process.

The following data have been included in the proof-of-concept platform:

- Domain Healthy - Indicators: Births and Health at birth, Immunisation, Physical health, Mental health, Injury, Substance use, Disability and chronic health conditions, Social emotional wellbeing, Sexual health, Hospital admissions, Mortality, ED presentations.
- Domain Learning – Indicators: Early childhood education and care, AEDC, NAPLAN, School attendance, Youth participation in education, Liking school, Sense of belonging at school.
- Domain Material basics - Indicators: Housing amenity, SEIFA, Stale housing, youth unemployment.
- Domain Valued, loved and safe - Indicators: Positive peer relationships, Family composition, Family conflict, Seeking support, Safe environments, Youth justice, Child protection, Children as victims of crime.
- Domain Participation – Indicators: Voting enrolment, Volunteering, Connection to community.
- Domain Identity and culture – Indicators: Country of birth, Language, Religion.

5. Pilot testing of Atlas, evaluation report

The pilot testing of the Atlas unfolded in multiple stages. Initially, the core project team conducted tests of the platform in collaboration and under the guidance of the QUT design team (VISER). This was followed by selected members of the Partnership group evaluating different platform elements.

However, a notable challenge emerged as the platform couldn't be extended to a larger pool of pilot testers without prior approval from data providers and custodians. The reason for this is that individual data sets cannot be isolated, so by reviewing one data set, all other data sets are technically accessible.

To address this, all custodians and data providers received a comprehensive data review pack containing their cleaned data files, metadata, screenshots showcasing their data in the platform, and a functional description. The Atlas could only be soft-launched once approval was received from all data providers, although it's noteworthy that two custodians withdrew their data post-review. The reasons are varied, yet none are definitive, and the project team is optimistic about including their data in future iterations (especially now that the Atlas is live).

Finally, the platform underwent a soft launch for stakeholders, partners, and supporters a few weeks before the official launch.

6. Publish national proof of concept Atlas incorporating Commonwealth and State data to support innovative research, best practice policy, and improved consistency and accuracy of monitoring the health and wellbeing of Australian children

The national proof of concept Atlas, the first Australian Child and Youth Wellbeing Atlas, was officially launched at Parliament House in Canberra on 28 November 2023. The Atlas is a free mapping resource that creates location-specific data of children and young people's health and wellbeing indicators.

<https://australianchildatlasmap.sph.uwa.edu.au/>

The Atlas includes 39 wellbeing indicators and about 400 data sets grouped into six domains displayed at local and national levels: health; learning; identity and culture; material basics; participation; and valued, loved and safe.

The wellbeing data in each statistical area is displayed alongside results for all Australian areas using different colours. Depending on the dataset selected in the Atlas, the score or measure can fall in a low, average, high, or in-between position on the national scale. Areas with results on the lower end of the scale are represented in shades of blue/green, those with results in or near the middle in shades of yellow/orange, and areas with results on the higher end of the scale are represented in orange/red/pink. Whether a high or low position on the scale is a good wellbeing outcome depends on the individual dataset or indicator.

For example, a low number of low birthweight babies is a good outcome (represented in blue/green) while a high percentage of children fully vaccinated is also a good outcome (represented in orange/red/pink).

The map of Australia can be zoomed in and out, similar to Google Maps.

For some indicators, the Atlas can switch between male only, female only, or all.

In this prototype, comparisons can be made between areas for one wellbeing dataset or indicator. Future development aims to include the capability to compare multiple indicators within one area and between areas.

For the prototype, a separate data download utility was developed called the Data Dashboard. This application allows a user to choose multiple regions, geographical resolutions, and disaggregations (theme, age, sex, collection year, and resolution where provided) and visualizes the results in tables. The data download utility enables the user to download both full and filtered versions of the data summaries by disaggregations. The data available in the data download utility is the same as that presented in the Atlas (except for those datasets where no permission for download was granted by the custodian).

A range of additional resources has been added to the site, including user guides, indicators information, and technical details.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

The data asset was officially launched at the end of November, coinciding with the end of the project period. Consequently, outreach and training activities have not been fully executed as of now. A comprehensive range of outreach initiatives is planned for 2024.

However, user design workshops were successfully conducted in 2023, and additional user evaluation workshops are on the agenda for 2024. Notably, some preliminary outreach efforts ('showcasing') were carried out as part of the community outreach activity for the WA Child Development Atlas (CDA).

To further support users, a suite of user resources is in development. This includes a detailed written user guide, an accompanying slide deck, and an instructional user video. These materials aim to enhance user understanding and engagement with the newly launched Atlas platform.

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
User design workshops	The workshops were conducted to inform the design of the visual and interactive elements of the Atlas. The user design workshops were recorded and transcribed, followed by a thematic analysis.	34	November 2022 – March 2023
Presentations	Online and in-person presentations about the Atlas to a wide range of audiences incl.: Child unlimited Conference in Brisbane, national showcase at Parliament House, Lottery west, InfoXChange, Healthway WA, Ian Potter Foundation, Paul Ramsay Foundation, Thriving Kids Queensland Partnership, Murdoch Children's Research Institute, National	100+	June – November 2023

	Centre for Place-based Collaboration (the Nexus Centre)		
CDA Community Information sessions	The community information sessions were held to promote the WA data asset and help community users get the most out of the resource. Given the move of the CDA data into the national atlas, the national Atlas was showcased to attendees.	100+	October-November 2023
Suite of user resources	Detailed written user guide, accompanying slide deck, an instructional user video	unlimited	Published November 2023
Potential users	The list of potential users includes: community members, clinicians, researchers, policymakers and analysts, not-for-profit organisations, educators, health professionals	unlimited	ongoing

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Current Funding Status:

The project team has successfully secured minimum or ‘bridging’ funding for the next two years, ensuring the ongoing operation, servicing, and maintenance of the proof-of-concept data asset. While the current funding allows for sustaining the platform, it does not permit further development or the addition of more data.

Securing Additional Funding:

The project team is actively pursuing additional funding from various sources:

Government Grants:

Ongoing applications for government grants, such as the Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF), to secure additional resources.

Philanthropic Funding:

Collaboration with key partners to explore philanthropic opportunities with a range of potential funders. This includes participation in the Investment Dialogue for Australia's Children initiative, showcasing the Atlas as a fitting candidate for support. We have been diligently working to promote the Atlas to additional funders.

Future Development Goals:

Upon securing new funding, the project aims to enhance the platform with the following features:

- **Unlocking State and Territory-Specific Data:** Expand the dataset to include more granular information at smaller community levels.
- **Diversifying Data Sources:** Incorporate non-administrative data, including surveys and cohort data, to provide a more comprehensive picture of child and youth wellbeing.
- **Additional Functionality: Overlay of Maps and Indicators:** Introduce overlay capabilities to enhance data visualisation, allowing users to correlate various indicators on maps.
- **Bespoke Community Reporting:** Develop customised reporting features to cater to the unique needs of different communities.
- **Inclusion of First Nations Children and Young People Data**
- **Regular reviews and adjustments to align with the evolving landscape of child and youth wellbeing data**

Monitoring and Evaluation:

Performance Metrics:

Establish key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the impact and usage of the platform.

Regularly assess the platform's performance against established KPIs.

Stakeholder Feedback:

Solicit feedback from users, partners, and stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and innovation. Hold user evaluation workshops in 2024.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	N/A DOI cannot be minted unless data is hosted in the UWA Library repository, and for several reasons, this is inappropriate (due to sensitivity of the data, data custodian requirements, etc)
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Comprehensive metadata document containing all indicators
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	Yes
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	Yes
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	N/A - see note under #1
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Yes (through the Data dashboard)
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	Yes (through the Data dashboard)
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	Yes (through the Data dashboard)
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on	Yes (through the Data dashboard)

	the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	N/A - see note under #1
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Yes
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	N/A - see note under #1
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	Yes
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	Yes
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Yes
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	Yes
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine-readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	Yes
18	The licence information is available in a machine-readable form on the landing	N/A - see note under #1

	page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	Yes on website
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	N/A
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	N/A

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

Please provide details of engagement with your community or stakeholders over the life of the project including: user community outreach, engagement or training activities undertaken; communication, promotional or editorial activities undertaken, including website pages, social media activity, media releases, articles, video content, etc; publications or published articles that mention the project or the data asset. Please list below and provide copies or links.

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Media release for official launch	Media release including promotional video	https://www.uwa.edu.au/news/article/2023/november/online-atlas-maps-childrens-health-and-wellbeing
Official launch	The first national showcase of the Atlas was held at Parliament House	https://www.uwa.edu.au/news/article/2023/november/online-atlas-

	<p>in Canberra on 28 November 2023. For the launch we partnered with the Future Healthy Countdown 2030 launch</p>	<p>maps-childrens-health-and-wellbeing</p> <p>https://www.vichealth.vic.gov.au/news-publications/research-publications/future-healthy-countdown</p>
Atlas website	<p>ACYWA website visits – monthly average November 2023:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of unique visitors: 622 • Visits: 873 • Page views: 1.8K 	<p>https://australianchildatlas.com</p> <p>https://australianchildatlasmap.sph.uwa.edu.au/</p>
Presentations	<p>Online and in-person presentations about the Atlas to a wide range of audiences incl.: Child unlimited Conference in Brisbane, national showcase at Parliament House, Lottery west, InfoXChange, Healthway WA, Ian Potter Foundation, Paul Ramsay Foundation, Thriving Kids Queensland Partnership, Murdoch Children’s Research Institute, National Centre for Place-based Collaboration (the Nexus Centre)</p>	<p>Generic ACYWA presentation to be placed on website in due course</p>
Partnership meetings	<p>We held sixteen (16) Partnership group meetings over the course of the project (2021-2023) to engage partners and progress the Atlas project</p>	<p>Link unavailable however documentation has been forwarded to ARDC program manager.</p>
Oversight Group meetings	<p>We held thirteen (13) Oversight group meetings over the course of the project (2021-2023) to provide governance for the project.</p>	<p>Link unavailable however documentation has been forwarded to ARDC program manager.</p>
Young People Advisory Group Meetings	<p>We held seven (7) meetings of the Young People Advisory Group</p>	

	(YPAG) between 2022 and 2023	
Working Group meetings	<p>Regular Working group meetings were held among the following Working Groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WG Data source identification, collection and research • WG Data linkage, analytics and visualisation • WG Future Funding • WG First Nations data 	
Project development website	<p>ANCHDA website visits – 6-month average:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of unique visitors: 400 • Visits: 461 • Page views: 607 	No longer available
User design workshops	<p>The workshops were conducted to inform the design of the visual and interactive elements of the Atlas. The user design workshops were recorded and transcribed, followed by a thematic analysis.</p>	Report to be published in due course
CDA Community Information sessions	<p>The community information sessions were held to promote the WA data asset and help community users get the most out of the resource. Given the move of the CDA data into the national atlas, the national Atlas was showcased to attendees.</p>	Report to be published in due course
Engagement with other ARDC Projects and community outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings with the National Poisons Information Centre Dataset • NDA Community Connect proposal - submitted 	
Logo design competition	<p>As part of our re-brand exercise that incorporates our new name ACYWA, a logo design competition</p>	https://australianchildatlas.com

	<p>was launched that included a social media campaign.</p> <p>The logo competition initiated a huge increase in the number of visitors to our website. Compared to the reporting period, traffic almost doubled in the 3 weeks of the comp period to date.</p> <p>Stats for 26 May – 16 June 2023 (3 weeks):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of unique visitors: 754 • Visits: 829 • Page views: 1.1K 	
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5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	Completed: Indicators for the Impact assessment framework have been established and relevant data collection has commenced.
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	Completed: user design workshops with relevant stakeholders including research users. Further user evaluation workshops planned for 2024 (post launch)
Partnerships with research translation specialists	We are working with our partners and networks across Australia.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	This has been established and relevant data collection has commenced.
Research Collaboration	Work has commenced to enhance collaboration between researchers, government agencies, policymakers, NGOs and community members through the use of the ACYWA platform.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

Reflecting on the journey of developing the first Australian Children and Youth Wellbeing Atlas, several elements stand out as instrumental and robust contributors to the success of the project.

Firstly, the governance structure established for the Atlas project played a pivotal role in ensuring effective coordination, communication and decision-making throughout the entire project lifecycle. The Oversight group, Partnership group, and Working Groups provided opportunities for clear lines of communication, accountability and input.

This structure not only facilitated smooth collaboration but also ensured the consideration of different perspectives at every stage due to the cross-sectorial makeup of members. The strength of our partnerships with agencies and stakeholders across multiple sectors including academia, government, not-for-profit, and the community was a clear success. The formation of a 'coalition of the willing' exemplified a collective commitment to challenge the status quo of the existing data landscape concerning children and young people from data collection, data sharing and publication. Our collective objective was to develop a publicly accessible, intuitive, and user-friendly data visualisation and mapping platform encompassing data on children and young people's health and wellbeing.

Moreover, the active involvement of a Young People Advisory Group is another key success factor. Direct input from children and young people proved to be invaluable in designing a new and bespoke platform. Their contributions served as a reminder of the project's ultimate purpose – to enhance the representation and understanding of the experiences of children and young people.

Equally crucial was the engagement of representatives from national data custodians, including organisations such as the AIHW. This ensured that the project was well-informed by existing data practices and aligned with current standards.

In summary, the success of our project can be attributed to the strength of our partnerships, the effectiveness of our governance structure, and the genuine inclusion of diverse voices, especially those of young people. As we conclude this project phase, these accomplishments serve as a foundation for future work aimed at further enhancing the functionality of the platform, navigating the data sharing landscape, and adding more data.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

In retrospect, the current landscape of children's health and wellbeing data in Australia presented some challenges to our project. One obstacle was the fragmentation of data sources, resulting in a complex and time-intensive data collection process. The intricacies of data processes, encompassing ethics applications, formal requests, sharing agreements, data identification, preparation, delivery, and review, consumed substantial time and resources, impeding optimal data collection outcomes.

A critical issue arose from the dispersion of data ownership, with national data collection bodies holding information owned by state and territory custodians. This dynamic complicates already intricate approval processes, often yielding unsatisfactory results despite the invested time and resources.

Further, accessing data from children and young people at the unit-record level or even just at granular (small area) levels proved to be a significant roadblock. The inaccessibility of such detailed information hampered our ability to include more data at small area levels and to conduct in-depth analyses or statistical manipulations effectively (e.g. calculating rates, moving averages etc). The data provided at macrolevels typically comes with cell suppression and lower data quality, rendering further analysis or recalculation challenging.

Given these challenges, it is imperative for the next project phases to consider collaborating with well-connected data liaison managers in each state and territory. These individuals will be better positioned to navigate the diverse data landscape in each jurisdiction. This collaboration is paramount to enhancing the overall quantity and depth of data on children and young people included in the Atlas.